

SURGICAL TREATMENT RESULTS OF VISCEROPTOSIS

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Abstract. *The authors report that manifestations of chronic dysfunctions of the colon in visceroptosis attract the attention of surgeons only at the stage of sub- and decompensated colostasis. However, prolonged conservative treatment and allowing the disease to progress to the sub- and decompensation stage is unjustified, as it often leads to a high recurrence rate—ranging from 17.6% to 45.9%. The authors conclude that complications in the early postoperative period were caused by certain shortcomings in preoperative preparation, determining the volume of the large intestine to be resected, the method of intestinal anastomosis formation, and postoperative management. This has necessitated adjustments in the surgical strategy for patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis.*

Keywords: *chronic colostasis, Visceroptosis, large intestine resection.*

Introduction. Visceroptosis (Glenard's syndrome, splachnoptosis, enteroptosis) is a condition in which the intestinal loops are positioned below their normal anatomical location. The disease develops due to the prolapse of internal organs, which is caused by the weakness of the reticuloendothelial system, rapid weight loss, and stretching of the abdominal wall [3;4]. Chronic dysfunction of the colon in visceroptosis attracts the attention of surgeons only at the stage of subcompensated and decompensated colostasis [7]. Researchers reasonably believe that prolonged conservative treatment of visceroptosis leading to sub- and decompensation is unjustified [2], as it often results in a high recurrence rate—ranging from 17.6% to 45.9% [1;6]. This issue is due to the imperfection of criteria for assessing colonic motility disorders and the lack of unified approaches in determining indications for surgical intervention, the extent of resection, and methods of forming interintestinal anastomoses.

The aim of the study. The aim of the study was to conduct a retrospective analysis of the surgical treatment outcomes of visceroptosis using traditional approaches and to identify the causes of complications and unsatisfactory results.

Materials and Methods. This study included 132 patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (CC) who underwent inpatient treatment at the coloproctology department of the Surgery and Civil Defense Department of the Clinic of Andijan State Medical Institute. In the clinical analysis of the studied patients, we adhered to the age classification adopted by the WHO [5].

Inclusion criteria: 1. age over 18 years; 2. verified diagnosis of visceroptosis combined with colostasis (CC); 3. elective nature of the pathology; 4. absence of acute infectious and inflammatory diseases; 5. written consent from the patient and their relatives for examination and treatment.

Exclusion Criteria: The exclusion criteria for the study were 1. combination of visceroptosis with nephroptosis or hepatoptosis; 2. urgent intestinal diseases; 3. acute cerebrovascular accidents and myocardial infarction; 4. acute infectious and viral pathology; 5.

colorectal tumors; 6. refusal of surgical treatment; 7. inability for further follow-up; 8. comorbid pathology in the decompensated stage.

In accordance with the study's objectives, the comparison group (2018–2022) consisted of 85 patients (64.4%), for whom a retrospective analysis of surgical treatment outcomes was conducted using traditional approaches.

To address the research objectives, clinical-laboratory, instrumental, and statistical studies were performed according to the latest standard methodologies, following the examination guidelines approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and Discussion. An analysis of gender distribution among patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis in planned surgical settings showed that men accounted for 16 cases (18.8%), while women constituted 69 cases (81.2%). The analysis demonstrated that the condition is predominantly diagnosed in females, with an average male-to-female ratio of 4.3:1.

Visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis was most frequently diagnosed in the 45–59 age group (mature age) in 43 cases (50.6%), representing the most economically active segment of the population, who are often exposed to external factors. Among patients aged 18–44 years (young age), 23 cases (27.1%) were diagnosed, primarily associated with congenital developmental anomalies. Patients aged 60 years and older (elderly age) accounted for 19 cases (22.4%), which could indicate excessively prolonged conservative treatment.

Surgical intervention was performed in 24 patients (28.2%) with a disease duration of 1–5 years, in 45 patients (52.9%) with a duration of 6–10 years, and in 16 patients (18.8%) with a disease duration of more than 10 years.

It is important to note that visceroptosis was most frequently diagnosed in patients with an asthenic body type—52 cases (61.2%), followed by a normosthenic body type—29 cases (34.1%), and least frequently in patients with a hypersthenic body type—only 4 cases (4.7%).

The clinical symptom complex of visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis consisted of both general and local symptoms. Constipation, as the primary manifestation of visceroptosis, was observed in 74 patients (87.1%), while alternating constipation and diarrhea occurred in 11 patients (12.9%). A sensation of heaviness in the abdomen was noted in 63 patients (74.1%), intestinal bloating in 58 patients (68.2%), and pain of varying intensity in 80 patients (94.1%). Abdominal sagging and striae were present in 17 patients (20.0%), diastasis of the anterior abdominal wall muscles in 5 patients (5.9%), and intoxication symptoms (weakness, dizziness, nervousness) in 55 patients (64.7%).

The degree of visceroptosis compensation was classified as follows: compensation (constipation lasting less than 3–4 days) was identified in 14 cases (16.5%), subcompensation (constipation lasting 5–10 days) in 41 cases (48.2%), and decompensation (constipation lasting more than 10 days) in 30 cases (35.3%). Among the types of visceroptosis, the smallest group consisted of patients with transversoptosis with deformation of the right flexure of the colon, which was identified in 14 cases (16.5%). Among them, the compensated stage was observed in 2 patients (2.4%), the subcompensated stage in 4 patients (4.7%), and the decompensated stage in 2 patients (2.4%).

The largest group consisted of patients with transversoptosis with deformation of the left flexure of the colon, which was diagnosed in 41 cases (48.2%). Among them, the compensated stage was observed in 12 patients (14.1%), the subcompensated stage in 26 patients (30.6%), and

the decompensated stage in 17 patients (20.0%). Additionally, transversoptosis with deformation of both flexures of the colon was detected in 30 cases (35.3%), with the subcompensated stage observed in 11 patients (12.9%) and the decompensated stage in 11 patients (12.9%).

Among the patients studied, the most frequently diagnosed comorbidities were cardiovascular diseases (IHD, hypertension, angina) in 14 cases (16.5%), hepatobiliary system diseases (type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic cholecystitis) in 6 cases (7.1%), chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (chronic bronchitis, pneumonia, bronchial asthma) in 5 cases (5.9%), and genitourinary system diseases (chronic pyelonephritis, cystitis) in 7 cases (8.2%).

Patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis had a history of various surgical interventions in 30 (35.3%) cases. Notably, cesarean section was relatively frequent, occurring in 13 (15.3%) cases, as well as surgical interventions for large ventral hernias and diastasis of the anterior abdominal wall muscles in 6 (7.1%) cases.

The analysis suggests that multiple pregnancies (cesarean section) and the presence of large ventral hernias with diastasis of the muscles play a role in the development and progression of visceroptosis. Additionally, a history of cholecystectomy was found in 2 (2.4%) cases, appendectomy in 5 (5.9%) cases, and hysterectomy with extirpation in 4 (4.7%) cases.

Of the total number of patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis (85), surgical treatment was performed in 62 (72.9%) cases. Colectomy was performed in 8 (9.4%) patients, subtotal colectomy in 16 (12.1%), sigmoid colon resection in 21 (24.7%), left-sided hemicolectomy in 12 (14.1%), and right-sided hemicolectomy in 5 (5.9%) patients. Conservative treatment was administered to 23 (27.1%) patients (including 12 (14.1%) in the compensation stage and 11 (12.9%) in the subcompensation stage).

In accordance with the research objectives, after surgical intervention in patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis, we conducted an analysis of short-term outcomes in the comparison group. This allowed us to identify the causes of unsatisfactory results and develop preventive measures during the course of this study.

We classified all postoperative complications into the following categories:

- **postoperative complications related to the formation of an intestinal anastomosis:** anastomotic suture failure with the development of peritonitis; anastomotic suture failure with the formation of a fecal fistula; postoperative anastomitis;
- **postoperative complications related to the extent of colon resection:** persistent constipation; diarrhea; recurrence of visceroptosis.
- **postoperative complications at the surgical wound site:** suppuration of the postoperative wound; infiltrate; ligature fistula.
- **general postoperative complications unrelated to the surgical intervention, which may also occur in other operations:** pulmonary embolism; hypertensive crisis; bronchopulmonary complications; others.

It should be noted that in assessing the outcomes of surgical treatment of visceroptosis in combination with chronic colostasis (CC) in the comparison group, the study had a retrospective nature.

Preoperative preparation, the choice of the extent of colon resection and the method of intestinal anastomosis formation, as well as postoperative management of this cohort, were carried out according to generally accepted standards. In this regard, we conducted a separate study of the

surgical treatment outcomes of visceroptosis in combination with chronic colostasis in both the comparison group and the main group.

In the comparison group, among postoperative complications related to the formation of an intestinal anastomosis, anastomotic suture failure with the development of generalized peritonitis was observed in 2 (3.2%) patients. Due to delayed diagnosis and, consequently, late reintervention, a fatal outcome occurred in 1 (1.6%) case. Anastomotic suture failure with localized process restriction and the formation of a fecal fistula was observed in 1 (1.6%) patient, which required a planned repeat surgical intervention (fistula closure). Postoperative anastomitis was noted in 2 (3.2%) patients, requiring prolonged and specialized conservative treatment.

Overall, complications characteristic of intestinal surgeries were observed in 5 (8.1%) patients in the comparison group, with a fatal outcome in 1 (1.6%) case. A retrospective analysis established that these complications were caused by certain shortcomings in preoperative preparation, as well as adherence to some traditional approaches in the formation of the intestinal anastomosis and postoperative management of patients in the comparison group.

Among postoperative complications related to the extent of colon resection, persistent constipation was observed in 5 (8.1%) patients, indicating an insufficient extent of colon resection. Diarrhea was noted in 4 (6.5%) patients, which, on the contrary, suggested an excessive extent of colon resection. Recurrence of visceroptosis was observed in 3 patients, indicating inadequate fixation of the ligamentous apparatus and an insufficient extent of colon resection.

As a result of the analysis, it was established that in determining the extent of colon resection and its fixation, there was an urgent need to refine the indications for selecting the appropriate surgical intervention and ensuring its proper fixation. Among postoperative complications, surgical wound suppuration was observed in 3 (4.8%) patients, wound infiltration in 3 (4.8%), and ligature fistula in 1 (1.6%) patient. Based on the analysis, we concluded that the systematic and targeted use of antibiotics, meticulous hemostasis along the surgical wound, and the use of modern suture material with an atraumatic needle are of paramount importance. In the comparison group, among general postoperative complications, pulmonary embolism was noted in 1 (1.6%) patient, indicating an insufficient scope of preventive measures, which should be carried out under the control of the coagulation and anticoagulation system of the blood. Hypertensive crisis was observed in 1 (1.6%) patient, reflecting inadequate antihypertensive therapy in a patient with hypertension. Bronchopulmonary complications were recorded in 4 (6.4%) patients, pointing to insufficient prophylaxis and appropriate therapy. Notably, 2 of these patients underwent surgery during the winter season and were chronic smokers.

Conclusion. Thus, the retrospective analysis revealed that the complications in the early postoperative period were caused by certain shortcomings in preoperative preparation, the selection of the resection volume of the large intestine, the method of intestinal anastomosis formation, and postoperative management. This necessitated adjustment in the surgical approach for patients with visceroptosis combined with chronic colostasis.

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